

Procedure for nucleus and breeder seed production of TGMS lines.

arranged so that the sensitive stage occurs when the temperature is favorable for higher seed set. At flowering, about 100 typical plants are selected from the population of a TGMS line and their panicles are bagged. The selection process is completed within a week. After harvest, selected plants are scored for spikelet fertility (based on the main panicle) and 50 plants with higher spikelet fertility are selected.

Progenies of the selected plants are grown in the sterility-inducing environment. About 30 seeds are taken from each of the selected plants to grow single row progenies and the remaining seed is stored carefully. Progenies that are uniform and completely male sterile are marked. The balance seeds of such selected progenies (stored earlier) are bulked to form the nucleus seed (see figure).

Nucleus seed is used to produce breeder seed under strict isolation. Breeder seed is produced in the fertility-inducing environment. The whole process of producing nucleus seed is repeated from the breeder seed plot. Fresh breeder seed should be used by seed production agencies to produce foundation seed of TGMS lines. The latter should be used to produce hybrid seeds. ■

Crop and resource management

Fertilizer management — inorganic sources

Response of promising rice genotypes to N levels in rainfed lowlands

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Rainfed lowlands in India constitute about 17 million ha, which is about 40% of the total rice area. Rice varieties selected for their nutrient require-

ments, particularly N, have great relevance for boosting overall production of rainfed lowland rice in India.

The performances of genotypes IET12199, IET10664, IET8655, IET12777, and IET5914 were compared with that of local check Gayatri at three N levels (0, 40, and 80 kg ha⁻¹).

The soil was sandy clay loam (Haplustalf), with a pH of 5.6, 0.40% organic C, and 230 kg available N ha⁻¹ (Kjeldahl method), 17 kg available P

ha⁻¹ (NH₄F extraction), and 280 kg available K ha⁻¹ (NH₄OAc extraction). The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design at CRLRRS with the genotypes in the main plot and N in the subplots with four replications.

Forty-five-day-old seedlings of different genotypes were transplanted during the first week of August. The recommended doses of 17.6 kg P ha⁻¹ and 16.6 kg K ha⁻¹, along with one-third of the N according to the treatment,

Table 1. Yield, yield attributes, N uptake, and agronomic N use efficiency of rice genotypes at different N levels. CRLRRS, Kharagpur, West Bengal, India. 1994 and 1995 WS.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	Agronomic N use efficiency (kg grain kg ⁻¹ N)
<i>N level (kg ha⁻¹)</i>					
0	2.1	217	2.31	45.9	-
40	3.1	235	2.56	70.2	24.0
80	3.3	247	2.70	90.7	15.1
LSD (0.05)	0.2	3.47	0.18	3.15	
<i>Genotype</i>					
IET12199	2.9	228	2.47	62.2	-
IET10664	2.9	230	2.48	67.3	-
IET8655	2.2	227	2.42	53.1	-
IET12777	2.2	222	2.27	49.5	-
IET5914	3.3	235	2.70	88.4	-
Gayatri	3.4	255	2.80	93.1	-
LSD (0.05)	0.7	13	ns	5.97	-

Table 2. Interaction effect of genotype and N application on yield, yield attributes, N uptake, and agronomic N use efficiency. CRLRRS, Kharagpur, West Bengal, India. 1994 and 1995 WS.

Variety	N level (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	Agronomic N use efficiency (kg grain kg ⁻¹ N)
IET12199	0	2.2	212	2.31	41.4	-
	40	3.0	230	2.47	63.3	20.0
	80	3.4	242	2.64	81.8	15.0
IET10664	0	2.2	214	2.32	44.8	-
	40	3.1	232	2.48	68.5	22.0
	80	3.4	244	2.65	88.6	14.8
IET8655	0	1.5	211	2.20	35.4	-
	40	2.5	229	2.45	54.1	24.5
	80	2.6	241	2.62	69.9	13.8
IET12777	0	1.4	206	1.81	32.9	-
	40	2.5	224	2.42	50.4	28.5
	80	2.6	236	2.59	65.1	15.5
IET5914	0	2.5	218	2.56	58.8	-
	40	3.5	237	2.73	89.9	25.0
	80	3.8	249	2.82	116.3	16.3
Gayatri	0	2.7	239	2.68	61.9	-
	40	3.7	257	2.85	94.8	24.5
	80	4.0	269	2.88	122.4	15.6
LSD (0.05)						
Between genotypes		0.654	12.60	ns	5.97	
Between N levels		0.182	3.47	0.188	3.15	
Variety × N level		ns	ns	ns	7.71	

were applied at transplanting. The remaining two-thirds of the N was applied in two equal splits at maximum tillering and panicle initiation.

Grain yield and N uptake increased with each increment of N up to 80 kg ha⁻¹, which registered the maximum yield as well as N uptake (Table 1). Grain yield was observed to be closely correlated with total N uptake ($r=0.899$). Increase in grain yield occurred mainly through the contribution of number of panicles m⁻². Weight of panicle increased consistently up to 80 kg N ha⁻¹, but agronomic efficiency decreased from 24.0 to 15.1 kg grain kg⁻¹ N at 40 and 80 kg N ha⁻¹, respectively.

Genotype Gayatri recorded significantly higher yield and N uptake than other genotypes but remained on a par with genotype IET5419. Most of the IET varieties had significantly lower N uptake than the check variety because of less N content in the plant sample and also because of total dry matter production. Yield and yield components also followed similar yield responses for different genotypes. Agronomic N use efficiency was higher in IET5914 and Gayatri than in other genotypes at 80 kg ha⁻¹. The gains may be attributed to the 84% higher yield recorded over that of the control (Table 2).

For rainfed lowland rice, none of the new genotypes tested outperformed the check variety Gayatri for high N use efficiency. ■

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Performance of Azolla hybrids in lowland rice culture

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Field experiments were conducted during the 1993 and 1994 dry seasons (June–September) to compare the effect of inoculation of *Azolla* hybrids and fertilizer N on rice yield. The experi-

ment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. The test soil was silty clay with a pH of 6.4, EC 0.45 dS m⁻¹, organic C 0.57%, 30.20 mol kg⁻¹ CEC, 320 kg available N ha⁻¹, 24.9 kg P ha⁻¹, and 273.9 kg K ha⁻¹. ADT36 rice seedlings were transplanted in 1.5-m² plots with 15- × 10-cm spacing. Superphosphate and potash as muriate of potash at 50 kg ha⁻¹ were applied as a basal dose. Nitrogen at 75 kg ha⁻¹ was applied as urea super granules (USG) alone and with *Azolla*.

USG was applied at 10 cm deep at 7 d after transplanting in between four hills of alternate rows, and prilled urea (PU) alone was applied in four split doses (40, 20, 20, and 20%) at basal, tillering, panicle initiation, and flowering stages for comparing with USG. *Azolla* hybrids AH-C1 (*A. microphylla* 4018 /*A. microphylla* 4028 (V3)), AH-C2 (*A. microphylla* 4018 /*A. microphylla* 4028 (V4)), and AH-C3 (strain of *A. microphylla* from China), and wild type *A. microphylla* (from Galapagos Islands) were